

“Global innovations in tourism”

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Global innovations in tourism

Abstract

The article is devoted to the increasing role of tourism in the world economy. The dynamics of international tourism indicators is investigated. The main global innovations in the tourism industry are identified: the growth of tourism types; the application of qualitatively new solutions of scientific and methodological and applied character; growing of tourism influence on the society; the existence of synergistic effect in the tourist industry as a result of combination of subjects efforts at all management levels; changing of the role of internal and external factors that encourage innovative tourism development. In the article, the interaction of global processes on tourism innovations is defined. These processes are: intellectualization, informatization, cooperation, formation of the global tourism market, liberalization of the national tourism markets, increased competition and the spread of transnationalization.

Keywords: tourism, innovations, globalization, world, type of tourism, innovative factors.

JEL Classification: L83, O32.

Introduction

Tourism is a phenomenon of the temporary relocation of human resources from their place of residence with the purpose of familiarization with and resource consumption of a new territory. It is one of the ancestral forms of the human resources movement, such as migration (long movement with the development of the new territories resources), transit and professional travel (spatial movement of workers associated with the crossing of territorial boundaries) and virtual movement (use of technical means of communication) (Sardak, 2015).

Today tourism is an important component of the world economy development. Over the past 20 years the tourism flows in the world have increased by more than 2.7 times from 436 million in 1990 to 1,186 billion people in 2015 (Appendix, Table 1).

After reaching a historic boom in 2012 – more than one billion people traveling the world in one year – the volume of international tourism continues to grow. This indicates about the rapid development of the world tourism industry. Europe will continue to lead in the number of tourists, which affects the flow of income from international tourism by world regions (Appendix, Table 2).

The table shows that the revenue is growing every year, and European continent has most of the income from international tourism which is evident during all years. Further on, America and Asia and

the Pacific region compete with each other: if from 2000 to 2005, America took the second place by revenues from international tourism, starting with 2006 and ending with the current time, Asia and the Pacific occupy the second place.

The dynamics of the data of Tables 1 and 2 shows the role of tourism for a society and allows speaking about the existence, the possibility and necessity of the global innovation study in tourism. This explains the intellectualization of the international movement of human resources. All this is understood as the prioritization of a knowledgeable component, the growth of educational and professional competence and achievements of individuals in the exercise of international mobility (Samoilenko, 2016).

1. Literature review

Aspects of innovative development of tourism were thoroughly researched by numerous scientists who comprehensively covered the global trends in innovative developments. So, B. Van Ark (2003), P. Putsenteylo (2007), M. Ronningen (2010), L. Carvalho and T. Costa (2011), S. Sardak (2013), A. Samoilenko (2016) identified existing and singled out growing types of tourism. R. Goehlich (2004), E. Anderson (2005), M. Van Pelt (2005), D. Baglieri, R. Consoli (2009), V. Pavlov (2012), O. Davydova (2015) identified qualitatively new decisions of the scientific and methodological, and applied character in the tourism sector. The materials of World Tourism Organization provided the possibility of determining the tourism global role in social development. S. Sardak (2012), P. Brouder and R.H. Eriksson (2013), V. Dzhyndzhoian (2016), V. Marakova and M. Medvedova (2016) noted the existence of synergistic effect in the tourism industry as a result of combination of subjects efforts at all management levels. R. Maklashina (2012), Martin (2013), Ali, Alisha and Frew, Andrew J. (2014), A. Williams (2014), R. Thomas and E. Wood (2014), F. Sorensen and J. Sundbo (2014) noted the changing

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role of internal and external factors that encourage innovative tourism development. In the study of the innovation components of the tourism market development, the question of detail determination of different levels of influence factors and innovative developments was not studied enough.

2. Aim of the study

The aim of the study is the identification and understanding of major global innovations in the tourism industry which were permanent throughout the XX century and continue to unfold at the beginning of the XXI century in the world.

3. Results

The analysis of scientific sources, which are listed in the literature review, allowed the authors to identify five key areas of the global innovation deployment in tourism. First, throughout the XX and XXI centuries, there has been a spread of tourism types. As a result of scientific sources analysis, we identified 16 classification features by which extend the types of tourism extend (Carvalho, Costa, 2011; Putsenteylo, 2007; Ronningen, 2010; Samoilenko, 2016; Sardak, 2013; Van Ark, Broersma and den Hertog, 2003).

By the territorial factor, we distinguish internal (intra-national) and international (foreign) tourism. By the direction of flow: incoming and outgoing. By the aim of the tour: recreation, health, therapeutic, informative (tour), professional, business, scientific (research, search, communication, conferences and congresses, scientific), educational (short term training), sports, shopping tours, adventure, pilgrimage, nostalgic (visiting relatives and places of origin), ecotourism (green tourism), exotic (thematic, sex tourism, alcohol, museum, theatre, esoteric (mystical), romance, war, historical, UFO tourism), elite (tourism to the North pole, exclusive tours, special terms and programs), ethnic (ethnographic, sentimental, family), amateur (hunting, fishing), extreme and combined types. By the sources of financing: social and commercial. By the way of travelling: pedestrian, aviation, marine, river, tourism by car, train, bicycle, horse-drawn, mixed. By the types of accommodation facilities: hotel, motel, guest house, friendly, sanatorium, hostel, camp, apartment, tents. By the number of participants: individual, family and group tourism. By the duration: short (short-term) and long-term tourism. Environment tours: mountain tourism, water, speleo-tourism, forest, desert, industrial, rural tourism, suburban tourism, urban tourism, aviation tourism, space tourism. By the flow rate: constant, seasonal, monoseasonal, bi-seasonal, event (one-time or periodic basis). By the institutional form of regulation: organized tourism, informal (amateur)

tourism. By the development and agreement with the receiving side: planned tourism and independent tourism. By the nature of the travel motivation: conveyor tourism and differentiated tourism. By the age of tourists: children, young people, tourism of relatively young economically active people, tourism of economically active people of middle age, tourism by pensioners. By the form of tourist services: inclusive tours, package tours. By the ethnic criterion: tourists have signs of national belonging, for example, an American tourist, a Japanese tourist, etc.

Second, innovation in tourism is confirmed by the appearance of new solutions of scientific and methodological and applied character in the existing types of tourism (Anderson, 2005; Baglieri, Consoli, 2009; Davydova, 2015; Goehlich, 2004; Pavlov, 2012; Van Pelt, 2005).

For example, in the field of restaurant tourism, restaurants are beginning to experiment with specialization (different national types of cuisine), specifically to focus on style, introduce additional services, cooperate, organize shows and workshops, actively engage the media and so on. The event tourism is growing in scale when one-time or on a periodic basis, large-scale international events are carried out: festivals, shows, artists' festivals, fairs, concerts, competitions, congresses and so on. In the field of the group tourism, the multi-purpose service is being introduced (for example, in the corporate tourism, there is the combination of business, entertainment, recreational, educational, pilgrimage tourism, etc.). In the sphere of social tourism, there has been the intensification of the volume of beneficial conditions for attracting different segments of population with the purpose of increasing the number of future tourists. It is possible to notice the development of depressive destinations, orientation tours for global values, promotion of national cultural heritage, distribution of social assistance. The part of scientific tourism is growing that will eventually complete the process of tourism transformation in the leading complex of world, scientific and cultural development. Space tourism is developing rapidly. The design of new space products and singling out fundamentally new tourism segments are developing: orbital, suborbital and near-earth parabolic flight providing training and sightseeing services in the space infrastructure.

Third, tourism as an activity is permanently changing the global society. Tourism is gradually making its contribution to addressing climate change and reducing poverty on the basis of a unified approach to this dual problem (World Tourism Organization). It is especially important for local agriculture, fisheries, handicrafts, construction

industry, transport, food production, small business. Tourism activities directly or indirectly determine the creation of jobs, stimulate private initiative, serves as a fulcrum for the development of the market economy which is conducive to small and medium enterprises. The tourism sector may significantly affect the environment. According to the conclusions of the World Tourism Organization, the top officials should consider the tourism sector as a means of ensuring sustainable development of the national economy, which will help to achieve a balance of environmental, economic and social aspects based on legislation and management grounds (World Tourism Organization). There are most important issues in the tourism sphere: reduced seasonal demand, support and enhancement of regional communities welfare, preserving and promoting the natural and cultural heritage, land use planning and monitoring development activities, application of standards and quality certificates, the monitoring and achieving of environmental trade-offs, staff development. All these can be achieved due to intellectualization – increasing the intellectual component in the implementation of the tourism movements (distribution of educational, professional, business, scientific, ethnic, and other types of tourism).

Fourth, innovation in tourism began to happen simultaneously at all managerial levels, which causes the synergetic effect from integration efforts of international organizations, regional associations, governments, local authorities, companies and tourists (Brouder, Eriksson, 2013; Dzhyndzhoian, 2016; Marakova, Medvedova, 2016; Sardak, 2012). So, coordination actions of international organizations, regional associations of countries and TNCs in the tourism market, the spread of strategic and global alliances, international law are developed at the global level.

The public authorities of the countries govern at the macro level: legislative policy (optimization of the legislation, improvement of state regulation mechanisms and formation of state power bodies and regulatory coordination structures), economic policy (formation of government guarantees, favorable investment climate, government programs, assistance in the training of qualified personnel and scientific exchanges, use of state standards); social and cultural policy (national branding, the formation of national image, national market). For example, in Ukraine, common innovations are the informatization of service technologies, the development of medical tourism, the creation of theme parks and ethnic tourism, the volume of the shows on television about tours and promotion of individual types of tourism, the growth of resorts, spas, recreation zones and parks and innovation structures of other types with

the rights of the special economic zones and territories of priority development, joining the world network of resort and health care institutions, the growth of passenger traffic by small aircraft.

At the meso level (enterprises of tourism infrastructure, associative structures, local governments), the intensifying of the cooperation between enterprises, distribution network and associative structures, the growth of strategic alliances, the creation of conglomerates and centers of cooperation with enterprises of other economic spheres, science and education, the establishment of regional centers visa and information services, implementation of the industry standards of service are going on.

At the micro level (the level of tourism enterprises), innovations are the following. Product: the creation of new tourist products and services, improvement of existing tourist products and services, development of new territories, development of new routes. Production: improvement of the quality of tourist services, attracting new resources, the growing use of new technologies (introduction of the possibility of virtual visits to places in 3-D and 5-D formats), computerization, automation of production processes (including QR codes, GPS navigation, scanners, sensors, tourist equipment, arranging means of transport), the greening of technology services. Marketing and promotion: popularization of the tourism businesses in the Internet environment, the increase of Internet technology volume, mass access and coverage of end-consumers, establishing permanent relationship with clients (database, network club programs, loyalty programs), the use of new forms of tourism product promotion (optimization for search engines (SEO), creating community brand, working with the blogosphere, personal distribution, the use of mapping systems), integration into the global booking system, the spread of sites-aggregators of the tourism offer, the introduction of virtual tours and virtual places. Management: application of progressive methods of control, automation control systems, the use of mobile applications for the administration and management of orders, improvement in providing information, attracting qualified personnel and improving personnel capacity, implementation of logistics management, improving internal and external communication of enterprises, the formation of global chains. On a personal level (tourists as consumers of tourism products), the following trends are identified. Needs: growing demands in tourism, a syndrome of “tourism dependence”, the increase of demands for tourist services, growth of the satisfaction level with the service received. Opportunities: growth opportunities of access to information, increase in free time, increasing

opportunities to travel, increasing feedback opportunities, increasing the possibility of pre-selecting and planning the tour due to Internet technologies, the implementation of virtual tourism. Action: prudence in the choice of tourism products, growth of communications in social networks.

Fifth, changing the role of internal and external factors that encourage innovative development of tourism (Ali, Frew, 2014; Clausen, Madsen, 2014; Maklashina, 2012; Martin, 2013; Pechlaner, Fischer & Hammann, 2006; Sorensen & Sundbo, 2014).

Modern views on innovation in tourism based on changes in society, which is under the influence of globalization processes has transformed into a "consumer society" and becomes the customer of new services. The number of such customers is increasing each year. Therefore, tourism enterprises also need to constantly transform. To ensure those innovation processes, it is expedient to apply the symbiosis of traditional and contemporary sections which includes: innovation focused on customer service; developing a highly innovative tourism products; the introduction of a specific innovative marketing policies; management of companies' innovation; direction of their activities towards cooperation with other representatives of the tourism industry at the local, regional and state levels. Tourism enterprises are becoming more subject to the influence of environmental factors, and internal factors experience adaptation.

Internal (endogenous) factors of the tourist market: demand processes, supply and distribution of tour product, the emergence of new intra-regional tourist segments, increasing the distance of travel, the variety of holiday forms, increasing short-term stay, increasing of tourism development diversification in established tourist space, the growth partnership of large companies with small and medium businesses, creation of strategic tourism alliances, the role of media in promotion, advertising and sale of tourism products, the number of employees, professional and qualification structure, the increase of professional training importance, improvement of organization work, the increase of private tourism business role and so on.

Static external factors:

- ◆ territorial-geographical: close to the sea, to mountain and forest areas, nature of coastline, the country's position in relation to the main suppliers of tourists, finding the region on important transit routes, etc.
- ◆ climatic: natural landscapes, rivers, lakes, waterfalls, seas, mountains, pleasant climate,

curative mud and mineral waters, temperature and wind condition, etc.

- ◆ historical and cultural: historical monuments, memorial places, museums, unique arts and crafts, customs and traditions of local residents.

External dynamic factors:

- ◆ social and demographic: the demographics of the population, age structure, degree of employment, the welfare of the population, the presence of singles and couples, the level of education and culture, the aesthetic requirements, the ratio of material and spiritual needs, urbanization, the level of performance of the health system, crime and the environmental situation, etc.
- ◆ economic: the economic situation in the country, financial stability, income levels, the share of funds allocated by society for tourism expenditure, commodity prices and so on.
- ◆ political-legal: crises, political instability, militarization of the economy, the tightening of tourist formalities, fluctuations of exchange rate, military conflicts, unemployment, cooperation in tourism sphere and other international economic relations, setting standards of tourist activities, the control of tourism through the administrative organs, etc.
- ◆ logistics: the development of accommodation, transport, service establishments, recreational areas, retail, etc.

In the XX century, a leading role in the world was first played by geographical, historical, cultural and climatic factors. Gradually, with the development of society, the leading role passed to social and demographic, economic and financial, logistical and political-legal factors. At the beginning of the XXI century, the influence of social and demographic and logistic factors markedly decreased. First place went to the economic and financial and political-legal factors. Extremely severe fluctuations in the exchange rate, the decline in prices of oil and other commodities and concerns about global security became major innovation factors that regulate the tourist flows. Therefore, it is not surprising that the USA, China, UK took first places in the world rankings of international tourism arrivals and receipts from international tourism. Steady rate of national currency in these countries allows tourists to be more secure in their desires and expenses. The energy independence of the United States, the use of innovation in the energy saving in China and the UK allow people to save on future travel. The distance from "explosive" areas, "hot spots" of the planet and effective security measures on the part of law enforcement give confidence to tourists to implement the desired trip or journey.

Findings

On the basis of the conducted research, we identified five key areas of deployment of global innovation trends inherent in the whole tourism sector: the growth of tourism; the application of qualitatively new solutions of scientific and methodological and applied nature; the growing influence of tourism in society; the existence of synergistic effect in the tourist industry as a result of the combination of subjects efforts at all management levels; the changing role of internal and external factors that encourage innovative tourism development.

The aforementioned major global innovations in the tourism industry occur due to the interference of other global processes: intellectualization as the growth of the intellectual component and people's change in the context of education and progressive development; informatization of all spheres of tourism companies; cooperation between the subjects of the tourism market; development of a global tourism market that involves all countries, the liberalization of national tourism markets; increasing competition; the transnationalization of the tourism companies activities.

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Appendix

Table 1. Dynamics and forecast of international tourism development*

Region	International tourism arrivals, million											
	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2020	2030
World	436	529	677	807	949	995	1038	1087	1138	1186	1360	1809
including:												
Advanced economies	297	336	420	459	506	530	555	582	615	653	643	772
Emerging economies	139	193	256	348	443	465	482	505	523	533	717	1,037
including by regions:												
Europe	262,7	305,9	388,0	448,9	485,5	516,4	539,6	566,3	588,4	607,7	620	744
Asia and Pacific	55,8	82,0	110,1	153,6	205,1	218,2	233,8	249,8	263,0	279,2	355	535
Americas	92,8	109,0	128,2	133,3	150,4	156,0	162,5	168,1	180,6	192,6	199	248
Africa	14,8	18,8	26,2	34,8	49,9	49,4	52,2	54,7	56,0	53,5	85	134
Middle East	9,6	13,7	24,1	36,3	58,2	54,9	49,8	48,2	50,3	53,3	101	149

* compiled by the authors according to World Tourism Organization.

Table 2. International tourism receipts, billion USD*

Year	World	Africa	Americas	Asia and Pacific	Europe	Middle East
2000	477	10,4	130,8	85,2	232,7	15,2
2001	464	11,5	119,8	88,0	227,7	15,6
2002	480	11,9	113,4	96,4	242,5	16,2
2003	524	15,5	114,1	94,9	282,9	16,8
2004	633	19,2	132,0	127,8	328,5	25,5
2005	676	21,7	145,2	134,5	348,8	26,3
2006	742	24,6	154,1	156,5	376,9	29,9
2007	858	29,1	171,3	186,8	435,2	35,0
2008	941	30,2	188,1	208,9	473,7	39,7
2009	851	28,8	166,2	203,1	410,9	42,0
2010	927	30,4	180,7	255,3	409,3	51,7
2011	1,042	32,7	197,9	298,6	466,7	46,4
2012	1,078	34,3	212,9	329,1	454,0	47,5
2013	1,197	35,5	264,2	360,7	491,7	45,2
2014	1,245	36,4	274,0	376,8	508,9	49,3

* compiled by the authors according to World Tourism Organization.